

THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TEACHER'S PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract:

The article explores, the professional competence of the teacher is professional and pedagogical opinions on determining the essence of all sub-competencies that make up the competence took place, and all other competencies were analyzed based on it and how to develop the intercultural communication competence of English language learners in English language teaching, as well as understanding the important goals of English language teaching.

Key words: professional competence, professional-pedagogical competence, linguistic, speech, discursive, socio-cultural, lingvodidactic.

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Development of professional competence of foreign language teaching and improvement orientation is stable cognitive, functional and personal components, that is, personal and professional requests of future teachers to meet, to develop their professionally significant personal qualities connect the auxiliary language tools with the standards of speech behavior to linguistic, social-cultural, subject, psychological-pedagogical knowledge and skills implies ownership. Therefore, researchers N.A. Gluzman and T. Poliser as they noted, taking into account many cognitive and personal factors, them full diagnosis and application, social and socio-cultural content in a foreign language organization of communication, as well as taking into account the professional interests of students obtaining and materials showing a high level of pedagogical competence in their work, it is necessary to use a wide range of methods, training manuals. Get information from students on each of these areas and that's it in the analysis of information from the knowledge of psychology, linguistics, sociology using the linguistic, socio-cultural, subject knowledge levels of students it is necessary to refer to the knowledge of pedagogy when choosing the appropriate material.

To the presentation of material in accordance with the style of mental activity of students communication competence in teaching a foreign language by choosing an approach an environment conducive to improvement and motivating is created.

The gap in teaching students about the language at school is in their higher education institution affects their education, it is difficult to replace it during professional training. The level of foreign language acquisition for preparation is only for students directly in their activities, that is, to their growing independence in learning a foreign language can be supported and increased.

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As a result of our research, we found that the professional competence of the English language teacher is professional-gnostic, so we understand that all the criteria listed below are interconnected. The development of an English teacher effective solving and analysis of practical tasks for the socialization of a person, self in a multicultural society understanding, effective interaction in the conditions of globalization of modern society, necessary pedagogical competencies and the ability to synthesize personal qualities and carry out intercultural communication, intercultural interactions, as well as value orientations, nature, society, people's spiritual experience and self-orientation providing favorable conditions for a person's successful integration into society through the development of this concept is the basis. In our opinion, language is the leading type of activity in the professional activity of an English teacher. Special attention should be paid to the communication process. Language communication is the goal and a tool of teaching English. Only by communicating with the language will the teacher achieve the stated goals of teaching English.

The English language is the basis for the implementation of all competencies included in the professional-pedagogical competence professional-linguistic competence of the teacher based on professional-gnostic. It really determines the structure of didactic activities for language acquisition. This competence is understood as an opportunity to perform the main professional functions of an English teacher.

The synthesis of necessary pedagogical competencies and personal qualities forms the basis of this concept formed by the teacher:

- 1) the ability to effectively solve practical tasks related to the socialization and formation of a developing person,
- 2) self-awareness in a multicultural society,
- 3) the ability to effectively influence the globalization process,
- 4) the ability to communicate between cultures, to carry out intercultural interactions;
- 5) value orientations, nature, society, and the development of the spiritual experience and self-orientation of people to provide favorable conditions for successful integration.

The concept of psychological-pedagogical competence in the science of pedagogy makes it possible to achieve quality results in the process of teaching and educating students. is defined as an adequate, proportional set of professional, communicative, and personal qualities of the teacher. The essence of teacher's psychological and pedagogical competence is clearly defined according the model of teacher's professional competence of educational standards and it includes the following:

- in adopting effective strategies for the teacher's individual approach to work with each student with individual characteristics, abilities, strengths of character of students, awareness of the advantages and disadvantages of training.

- awareness in the field of communication processes that occur in groups where the teacher works, among students and between the teacher and the groups, the teacher and the students, and the processes taking place within the groups, how communication processes contribute to or hinder the achievement of the desired pedagogical information about results.

- teacher's best teaching methods, professional self-development skills, as well as his/her own strengths and weaknesses of his personality and work, what he can do to improve the quality of his work awareness of what to do.

Lingvodidactic and methodological competence to implement the successful pedagogical activity of the English language teacher is the most important component of professional-pedagogical competence, because it is the main competence negates the meanings: taking into account the teacher's way of thinking, pedagogical ethics, and social

functions having the importance, knowledge and experience, which is a system of knowledge.

Methodological competence, on the one hand, is the teacher's ability to teach his subject to students, on the other hand, implies the necessity and skill of self-education.

In conclusion, there are four that form the professional-pedagogical competencies of an English teacher interdependence of sub-competence is an opportunity to perform basic pedagogical functions. However, this implementation of functions occurs on the basis of the activity of professional-gnostic competence of the English language teacher. Each of the functions implies the formation of professional-gnostic competence.

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